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Serious Game Development - Entrepreneurship as the context for Engineering Education

Carina Lomberg
Assistant Professor
DTU Management
Technical University of Denmark
calom@dtu.dk

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INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we conceptualize an innovative and sustainable teaching way that motivates and engages to study engineering by providing an entrepreneurial context. More specifically, we describe the development of a serious educational game that combines educational learning theory with existing frameworks for game development into one coherent framework. We specify this framework with regard to teaching engineers by letting them take on the role of an entrepreneur.

1 SERIOUS EDUCATIONAL GAMES

A serious educational game (SEG) is a computer-based game with the primary purpose of education. SEG allow the educator to connect real-world scenarios with specific learning objectives [1]. These games have been shown to address both the cognitive and affective dimensions of learning [7], and hence, enable players to adapt learning to their cognitive needs, and provide a higher intrinsic motivation for learning. They have further shown to provoke active player involvement and deep learning through hands-on exploration and experimentation and increased visualisation [9]. Particularly for a generation that is more digitally sophisticated than any generation previously, SEGs provide a learning method that suits the students'

personal preferences for learning at a pace that they chose themselves. Therefore it is not surprising that SEGs have become widely adopted by a new generation of learners, who has grown up immersed in new communication technologies [8].

However, whereas educators and games share the idea that participants have to achieve some goal, the goals of a SEG and the learning objectives often do not match. When designing a SEG, a dedicated framework for educational games is lacking [8]. Among the available frameworks, most are rather technical and hence, provide advice for how to bridge game design, game criticism and technical game research [2]. Yet, frameworks that specifically link game development with educational objectives are rare [5]. Those that deal with learning objectives typically address physical classroom games or massive multi-user online games but leave out critical elements of SEGs such as game complexity. In what follows, we hence develop a coherent framework based on models for SEG development and educational learning theory and specify this framework with regard to the topic of our educational game: entrepreneurship as the context for engineering education.

1.1 The Developing Perspective – Subsystems of SEGs

When developing SEGs, three levels have to be taken into account: the conceptual level, the technical level, and the practical level. The conceptual level comprises a set of interrelated elements and specifies how they interact with each other and develop over time. The conceptual level creates the dynamic in the game. It needs to be a closed self-contained environment, which can be reached with a decision tree that incorporates all possible paths a player, can take. The technical level describes the tooling system for the system architecture. This concerns the management of the game when in use later. The practical level provides principles for how to reduce complexity (e.g. by providing relevant information in form of a tutorial). Yet, these subsystems do not take into account the learning experience.

Fig. 1. Developing Perspective

1.2 The Learning Perspective – Bloom's taxonomy

To determine how effective SEGs are, the quality of learning should be assessed with regard to the extent the game helps players to reach the learning objectives of the course/class. To guide such an assessment, researchers have developed taxonomies on the basis of learning objectives. In this regard, Bloom's taxonomy and its revised version [2] became most popular. The revised taxonomy is a hierarchical model that includes six major categories in cognitive processing: *Remembering*,

Understanding, Applying, Analyzing, Creating, and Evaluating (cf. Fig 2). The taxonomy helps classifying educational system goals to support educators to achieve learning at a deep level in their students. Such deep learning occurs on the higher levels of the taxonomy (i.e., analyzing, creating and evaluating). Hence, for our SEG development, the learning objectives should focus on these higher levels and guide the game structure and design. They also serve as a control for curriculum alignment once the game is finished.

Fig. 2. Bloom's revised Taxonomy

Fig. 3. A Nested Model of SEGs

1.3 The Education Perspective – A nested Model of SEGs

Whereas Bloom's taxonomy has the students' learning in mind and is based on cognitive theory, educational advices for how to design SEGs from an educator's perspective are often based on experience and research from commercial videos games. For instance, [1] proposes a nested model for SEGs that include "identity", "immersion", "interactivity", "increasing complexity", "informed teaching" and "instructional" (cf. Fig 3).

Giving the player an *identity* in form of an (ideally self-chosen) avatar is important for the players' individuality, subsequent engagement in the game and effort. Without an identity the experience is less authentic and the learning less intense. *Immersion* creates an intrinsic motivation (or even flow) to the player. Intuitive usage, clear goals and appropriate feedback create immersion whereas inappropriate challenges and a user-unfriendly interface hinder the engagement. *Interaction* with other player or the computer is essential for creating authenticity and fosters players to react in a similar as they would do in a real-world scenario. Interaction keeps the player engaged and active. *Increasing complexity* helps to ensure deep learning experiences. If the challenges are gradually increasing, the players reach at some point the pinnacle of flow. This state is also called *pleasurable frustration* and describes situation that is exciting but difficult. This state is the confluence of deep learning and good gaming [1]. If too complex challenges come to early, the player is just frustrated and does not reach deep learning levels. *Informed teaching* describes

the virtual observations of students (e.g. via log-ins, past decisions, process in the game). These virtual observations inform the educator about progress and learning and allows for tailored feedback and coaching. *Instructional* refers to students that are engaged in an SEG in such a way that learning is stealthy, i.e. that students do not realize that they are learning. If SEGs are designed well, they influence learning by connection a link between virtual game reality and real life and thereby influences long-term memory, and encourage critical thinking. This is the ultimate goal for educators and arguable challenging to develop.

Taken together, for developing our SEG, several levels have to be taken into account: the conceptual – technical level, the students learning, and educator's role in providing the learning. Fig 4 integrates the elements into one framework.

2 TEACHING ENTREPRENEURSHIP THROUGH A SERIOUS GAME

2.1 SEGs and Entrepreneurship Skills

Today's offer of SEGs primarily focuses on providing topic-related skills in either engineering or Entrepreneurship (e.g., Marketplace Venture Strategy, SimVenture, Virtual Trader, Intopia, Beer Game, Zapitalism, Virtual U, Industry Giant II, Virtual U, Innov8, EagleRacing, The Enterprise Game, The Finance Game, MetaVals). To date, none of the games combines engineering education with an innovation-related career as entrepreneur, scientist or innovation facilitator. Moreover, although there is a strong need for long-term behavioural training, simulations today focus on skills only. Research has shown, however, that a number of nascent entrepreneurs drop their venturing idea because they lack self-confidence, persistence, and the ability to shield their intention against drawbacks and obstacles along pursuing their goals. Likewise, in engineering education, grades are usually below those in social sciences and other subjects. This does not only prevent students with a low self-confidence from starting an engineering education, it also inheres uncertainty in the belief of successfully finishing the chosen study path. Particularly women lack confidence in their skills when the environment is uncertain and provides a risk for failure.

With an educational tool that trains and reinforces behavioural components, we aim at overcoming the lack of confidence, persistence, and tolerance for ambiguity related to engineering skills and STEM based career paths in innovation. As every entrepreneur shows specific traits such as persistency, self-efficacy, and a low fear of failure, we expect boys and girls alike to benefit from an integrated behaviour-related training within our simulation.

2.2 Status quo: Entrepreneurship SEGs and Learning Outcomes

SEGs in entrepreneurship have not been reviewed comprehensively with regard to technical and educational aspects. However, [4] have reviewed the most commonly played SEGs (i.e., Hot Shot Business, SimVenture, and Any Business) with regard to Blooms revised taxonomy [3]. They conclude that with regards to the learning goals remembering, applying, and analyzing, existing SEGs are helpful. Through images,

animations and compelling situations, and the repetitive nature of many games, remembering is supported. The learning-by-doing approach supports the application and the variety of analytics and documentation tool provide real-time feedback to the players, and hence, help assessing the students' performances. Hence, these positive elements should be kept.

With regard to understanding, the available games are not very efficient as they lack supervision and in-depth information. With regard to the highest levels of learning – evaluating and creating – [4] conclude that current games lack an understanding of the effects of the player choices and suggest supervision by a teacher to improve the player's assessment and improvement through appropriate indications and suggestions. Given the scripted nature of SEGs, creating is limited. Technical advancements such as machine-learning-based classifiers might overcome this problem. These elements allow for improvement.

2.3 Applying Educational Game Design Elements to Entrepreneurship

Taking together, we aim at keeping the benefits of existing games and overcoming their limitations with a game that 1) provides an immersing “real-world” experience by providing realistic, compelling and impactful cases students can choose from based on their engineering specialization. The game should 2) allow for reflective observation by a variety of graphics and data and reflection tasks, and 3) active experimentation. The experimentation might lead to 4) drawbacks in the game to create challenges on an increasing level and but allows for failure in a safe gaming environment that should prevent 5) frustration. The games will be structured in 12 sessions – with feedback after each session to provide 6) interaction and informed teaching. To provide 7) abstract conceptualizations (e.g. theoretical foundations), the game will be played in parallel to classroom teaching. To allow for different levels of experience in students, we will also provide 8) tutorials within the game that players can consult before making decision. To reach highest levels of learning, the players won't be assessed on their performance but on their 9) reflections on critical decision with regard to course content and personal experience while playing the game.

Fig. 4 An Integrated Framework for Designing SEGs

3 CONTRIBUTION

3.1 Player/Student

Our game will provide a hands-on start-up experience that embeds the learning in a playful environment. It will jointly increase specific engineering and entrepreneurship knowledge, but also impact the students' intrinsic motivation. The game will provide a close link of students' newly acquired skills to a possible career-path and thereby show the usefulness of their education for their future occupation. It will provide additional training of personality and behavioural components (such as persistence, reduced fear of failure) that will increase students' self-efficacy and thereby help to reduce dropout rates in general. After playing the game, students will be encouraged and better prepared to create successful start-ups within their engineering domain.

3.2 Educator

From an educator's perspective, teaching bigger groups of students prevents the close monitoring of each and every student. Traditional ways of teaching have to be generic enough to address a broader group of students. The amount of time and costs needed to provide very specific support and training prevents a teaching style that takes into account individual learning styles and preferences. Our SEG will provide a cost- and time-effective way of improving each student's skills and behaviour and provide additional specific training where needed. The flexibility of the tool makes it is useful for a variety of target groups starting from young pupils, high-school students, early-stage students and students that are close to their graduation.

3.3 Researcher

As for researchers, the analytical power—both predictive and prescriptive—may serve as a basis for better understanding how students learn based on their behavioural traits. Moreover, researchers will get some valuable insights of the process of nascent entrepreneurship. There is increasing recognition amongst researchers of the need to study the process of entrepreneurship rather than view it as a single entrepreneurial act. To date we have a limited understanding why some individuals who embark on an entrepreneurial journey persist and succeed to build a sustainable venture while others show a lack of progress or drop out altogether. The information we will get from the quasi-longitudinal simulation dataset will provide some new insights in the process.

4 CONCLUSION

Developing a game that supports detailed in-depths practical aspects of a "learning-by-doing"-approach with a broad and more generalizable theoretical underpinning is challenging as it implies finding a balance between abstraction and application, reflection and fun. We hope that the combination of having a game complementary to traditional classroom teaching allows for reaching such balance. The results of the pilot testing will show whether we have reached our goals of creating an innovative learning tool that simultaneously provides deep learning and the inspiration and encouragement of becoming an entrepreneur within a technical domain.

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